

Toward dithia-aza based malachite green probe : Colorimetric chemosensor for Hg²⁺ ions

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Abstract : A new probe **1** based on a malachite green derivative bearing two dithia-aza subunits was prepared, and studied as colorimetric chemosensor for the sensitive detection of Hg²⁺ ions over other representative metal ions.

Keywords : Hg-sensor, dithia-aza, malachite green, naked-eye.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been growing interest in the development of chemosensors for the sensitive detection of mercuric (Hg²⁺) ion because of its toxicity causing serious problems for public health and ecology¹⁻⁵. Although a number of molecular probes for the detection of Hg²⁺ ions have been developed, colorimetric chemosensors for the selective detection of Hg²⁺ are quite attractive because of their excellent sensitivity, rapid response, and ability to do the so-called “naked-eye” detection in a straightforward and inexpensive manner⁶⁻¹⁴. Thus, developing simple and practical colorimetric chemosensors for Hg²⁺ ions is still a challenge. However, dithia-aza binding motif is currently used^{15,16} in the design of chemosensors owing to its ability to coordinate specific metal ions through N and S-donors. Furthermore, the malachite green entity is one of the most attractive chromogenic units due to its well characterized UV-Vis absorption and easy synthesis. To continue our interest in chemosensor development for transition and heavy metal ion monitoring¹⁷, we report herein a simple malachite green (MG) derivative **1** as colorimetric chemosensor bearing dithia-aza chelating units for the rapid detection of Hg²⁺ ions in aqueous media. Malachite green (MG) **2** was taken as reference compound. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no report on the design of MG-derivatives for “naked-eye” detection of Hg²⁺ ions.

Results and discussion

N-Phenyl-5,11-dithia-8-azapentadecane **1a** was synthesized according to the Scheme 1. **1a** was then condensed with benzaldehyde to give **1** in good yield. Titled molecule **1** was characterized by FT-IR, UV-Vis, NMR, MS, and elemental analyses. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of **1** in THF-water (4 : 1, v/v) solution ([**1**] = ~4.9 × 10⁻⁵ M) exhibited three absorption bands at 307, 435 and 625 nm (weak) (ε = 1.01 × 10⁴, 6.42 × 10², and 1.42 × 10³ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively) typical of MG subunit. Absorption titra-

Scheme 1. (i) *p*-TsCl, pyridine, 0–5 °C (80%); (ii) (a) Thiourea/EtOH, reflux, (b) NaHCO₃/H₂O, 80–90 °C; (iii) (a) dry THF/NaH, reflux, (b) *n*-BuBr, rt, 65%; (vi) (a) PhCHO, ZnCl₂ (anh.), THF (dry), reflux, (b) PbO₂, conc. HCl, water, rt, 70%.

tion experiments were carried out by using the set of representative metal ions, such as Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ (all as sulphates), Pb²⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺ (all as perchlorates) and Hg²⁺ (as nitrate) to evaluate the metal ion binding selectivity and sensitivity of **1**.

Upon interaction with this set of metal ions, only Hg²⁺ induced a progressive and sizable increase in absorption band at 626 nm. Fig. 1 gives detailed UV-Vis spectral changes of **1** upon titration with Hg²⁺ ions. Remarkable feature pertaining to this molecular probe is the change of color from light yellow to greenish blue (Fig. 2) which can be used for a “naked-eye” detection of Hg²⁺ ions in aqueous solution.

No significant color/absorption changes were observed upon interaction with other potentially competing metal ions mentioned (Figs. 2 and 3) demonstrating its unique selectivity and sensitivity toward Hg²⁺

Fig. 2. Color changes of **1** ($4.9 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon the addition of tested metal ions in THF-water (4 : 1, v/v).

ions. The stoichiometry of the complex (**1**.Hg²⁺) in the interaction process was determined from the titration curve (Fig. 4). The break of the titration curve at Hg²⁺/[**1**] = 2 indicates the formation of 1 : 2 complexes (sensor **1** : Hg²⁺ ion).

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectral changes of **1** ($4.9 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon the incremental addition of 14 equivalents of Hg²⁺ ion in THF-water (4 : 1, v/v).

Fig. 3. Plot of absorption intensity at 625 nm as a function of metal ion concentration.

The signaling mechanism might be attributed to the Hg²⁺ chelation induced perturbation of the π -clouds of non-planar propeller-like twisted structure (A) toward the corresponding more conjugated quinoid-like cationic forms (B and C) as illustrated in Scheme 2. Both nitrogen and sulfur atoms of dithia-aza subunit participate in Hg²⁺-ion binding cooperatively.

In order to look into the thiophilic speciality in the chelation induced absorption effect in **1**, UV-Vis titration experiments of well known reference compound **2** lacking S-donors were carried out. We noticed that adding Hg²⁺ to the solution of **2** induced no change in color/absorption features. This observation revealed that the presence of two proximal S-donors is a prerequisite for promotion of M^{x+}-N interaction induced signaling mechanism.

The complexation induced signaling phenomenon of **1** with, for instance, Hg²⁺ ions was further evidenced by LCMS and ¹H NMR measurements. The

¹H NMR spectrum of **1** in the presence of Hg(NO₃)₂ was broadened to some extent and resulted in downfield shifting of the MG-protons, especially in the dithia-aza moiety. These shifts suggest that dithia-aza moieties are involved in the coordination with Hg²⁺ ions. LCMS measurement provided additional evidence for the formation of 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the complex **1**-Hg²⁺.

Conclusion

In summary, dithia-aza based malachite green chemosensor **1** has been synthesized for the first time. A distinct color change was observed when **1** was treated with Hg²⁺ ions. This is presumably attributed to the perturbation of the π -system upon complexation of Hg²⁺ ions at the binding domains. Such impressive color change as well as the high reproducibility and the large persistence (days) of the coloration of probe **1** permit a “naked-eye” detection of Hg²⁺ ions in aqueous media. Work in this direction is currently under progress in our laboratory.

Experimental

Synthesis of 1a : A solution of aniline (0.5 g, 5.38 mmol), 2-chloroethanol (4.3 g, 53.76 mmol), and calcium carbonate (2.5 g, 25.0 mmol) in 50 ml water was refluxed for 18 h, and the filtrate was extracted with dichloromethane. The organic phase was dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* to get the crude product, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel eluting with petroleum ether gradually increasing to 1 : 1 petroleum ether/EtOAc to obtain pure product of *N*-phenylated diethanolamine (70%). Conversion of *N*-phenylated diethanolamine to the corresponding dithiol was achieved by following the reported procedure¹⁵.

Fig. 4. Plot of absorption change of **1** at 625 nm as a function of [Hg²⁺]/[**1**].

Scheme 2. Suggested co-ordination induced sensing mechanism of **1** for Hg²⁺ ions.

Under nitrogen atmosphere, to a solution of the corresponding dithiol (0.154 g, 0.723 mmol) in dry THF was added NaH (0.0696 g, 2.90 mmol) and refluxed for 2 h. Then *n*-butylbromide (0.397 g, 2.90 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture and stirred overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was redissolved in EtOAc, washed with brine solution, dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* to get the crude product, which was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 60–120, petroleum ether/EtOAc 1 : 50) to obtain pure product **1a** (65%). FT-IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2957, 2929, 2862, 1591, 1505, 1458, 1343, 1277, 1181, 1143, 743, 686 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz) δ : 7.23 (2H, t, *J*=7Hz), 6.70 (1H, t, *J*=7Hz), 6.66 (2H, d, *J*=8Hz), 3.52 (4H, t, *J*=7.5Hz), 2.71 (4H, t, *J*=7.5Hz), 2.57 (4H, t, *J*=7.5Hz), 1.62–1.56 (4H, m), 1.46–1.38 (4H, m), 0.92 (6H, t, *J*=7.5Hz). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₃₁NS₂ : C, 66.40; H, 9.60; N, 4.30. Found : C, 66.38; H, 9.59; N, 4.28.

Synthesis of 1 : Compound **1a** (0.02 g, 0.061 mmol) was dissolved in minimum volume of dry THF. Benzaldehyde (0.0016 g, 0.0153 mmol) was then added into the solution of **1a** and the resulting solution was refluxed with anhyd. ZnCl₂ for 24 h. After solvent evaporation, the residue was treated with water, PbO₂ and few drops of conc. HCl. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight. Then the mixture was treated with water and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic phase was dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The crude product obtained after removal of solvent was purified by preparative thin layer chromatography using 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether to yield **1** (70%) as a green semisolid. FT-IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2930, 2859, 1726, 1596, 1510, 1453, 1386, 1348, 1281, 1167, 1119, 1024, 891, 814, 691, 614 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz) δ : 7.28 (4H, d, *J*=10Hz, ArH), 7.12–7.06 (5H, m, ArH), 6.96–6.90 (2H, m, ArH), 6.54 (2H, d, *J*=10Hz, ArH), 3.94–3.91 (4H, m), 3.55–3.51 (4H, m), 3.07–3.05 (4H, m), 2.90–2.80 (4H, m), 2.73–2.71 (6H, m), 2.62–2.60 (2H, m), 1.73–1.70 (4H, m), 1.42–1.40 (4H, m), 1.29–1.21 (8H, m), 0.94–0.86 (12H, m); ¹³C (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) δ : 141.5, 130.3, 129.7, 129.5, 129.3, 128.9, 127.8, 120.4, 116.6, 116.0, 110.4, 81.0,

70.0, 52.3, 51.8, 51.5, 44.7, 41.1, 32.1, 29.7, 26.7, 14.1, 13.7. Anal. Calcd. for C₄₃H₆₅N₂S₄.Cl : C, 66.75; H, 8.47; N, 3.62. Found : C, 66.80; H, 8.53; N, 3.60; *m/z* (ES⁺) 772.4 (M⁺), 737.7 (M–Cl)⁺.

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References

1. D. W. Boening, *Chemosphere*, 2000, **40**, 1335.
2. P. B. Tchounwou, W. K. Ayensu, N. Ninashvili and D. Sutton, *Environ. Toxicol.*, 2003, **18**, 149.
3. R. K. Zalups and L. H. Lash, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.*, 2006, **214**, 88.
4. T. Syversen and P. Kaur, *J. Trace Elem. Med. Biol.*, 2012, **26**, 215.
5. K. Kim, E. Kabir and S. A. Jahan, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2016, **306**, 376.
6. (a) Y. K. Yang, K. J. Yook and J. Tae, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 16760; (b) J. S. Lee, M. S. Han and C. A. Mirkin, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, **119**, 4174.
7. X. Chen, T. Pradhan, F. Wang, J. S. Kim and J. Yoon, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 1910 and references therein.
8. H. Y. Lee, K. M. K. Swamy, J. Y. Jung, G. Kim and J. Yoon, *Sens. Actuators B : Chem.*, 2013, **182**, 530.
9. F. Yan, M. Wang, D. Cao, N. Yang, Y. Fu, L. Chen and L. Chen, *Dyes Pigm.*, 2013, **98**, 42.
10. Y. M. Zhang, W. J. Qu, G. Y. Gao, B. B. Shi, G. Y. Wu, T. B. Wei, Q. Lin and H. Yao, *New J. Chem.*, 2014, **38**, 5075.
11. X. Cheng, Q. Li, C. Li, J. Qin and Z. Li, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2011, **17**, 7276.
12. G. Sener, L. Uzun and A. Denizli, *Anal. Chem.*, 2014, **86**, 514.
13. S. B. Maity, S. Banerjee, K. Sunwoo, J. S. Kim and P. K. Bharadwaj, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2015, **54**, 3929.
14. P. Venkatesan, N. Thirumalivasan and S.-P. Wu, *RSC Adv.*, 2017, **7**, 21733.
15. S. J. Lee, J. H. Jung, J. Seo, I. Yoon, K.-M. Park, L. F. Lindoy and S. S. Lee, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 1641.
16. C. S. Park, J. Y. Lee, E.-J. Kang, J.-E. Lee and S. S. Lee, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 671.
17. S. Ghosh, C. K. Dey and R. Manna, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 3177.
18. S. Ghosh and R. Manna, *Supramol. Chem.*, 2011, **23**, 558.
19. S. Ghosh and R. Manna, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 5798.